

Creating a Framework for the Representativeness Assessment of Automated Driving Safety Assurance
28th ITS World Congress, Los Angeles, September 18-22, 2022

Paper ID 1228116

Creating a Framework for the Representativeness Assessment of Automated Driving Safety Assurance

Johannes Hiller*¹, Svetlana Kalyagina², Lutz Eckstein¹

1. Institute for Automotive Engineering (ika) RWTH Aachen University, Germany (johannes.hiller@ika.rwth-aachen.de)

2. RWTH Aachen University, Germany

Abstract

Over the past years, automated driving has moved towards a stage, where the public introduction of automated driving functions (ADF) seems conceivable. However, the question of verification and validation of these systems as well as assuring their safety is still a discussion among researchers, manufacturers, and authorities. Whilst the approach of scenario-based testing has established itself for this task in research and application, open questions remain regarding the relevance of scenarios and their needed representativeness. Within this paper, we present a framework which can help with this task by taking different data sources into account to assess the representativeness of scenario parameters in these data sources as well as in recorded data. As scenario parameters apart from traffic participants we take weather and road parameters into account. Within the research project Hi-Drive, enabling the ADFs to deal with these parameters is an important topic of research.

Keywords:

Safety assurance, automated driving, scenario parameters

Introduction

Automated driving comes with the claim of relieving the driver of his supervision task to some extent. To this end, systems are developed which perceive the environment and act upon these external factors. However, due to the wide range of different parameters and influences the environment as well as the vehicle itself has, this increasingly proves as a hardship for the approval of automated vehicles. The classical approach of distance-based testing is no longer sufficient to address this issue, considering the many kilometers that would need to be covered (WACHENFELD et al., 2016). To overcome this issue, scenario-based testing has established itself as possible solution (ZLOCKI et al., 2015). The basic idea is to split up the testing into scenarios where each scenario is in some way relevant to the safety of the tested function. Each of these scenarios can be stored in a database for efficient testing (PÜTZ et al., 2017). Looking at the processes so far, it becomes clear, that not every eventuality is considered yet for the testing. Taking into consideration the reasons for accidents, it becomes clear, that factors apart from other traffic participants need to be considered. As an example, somewhere between 2.5% and 11.4% of accidents in Germany in the years 2012-2014 were related to severe weather conditions (RÖSENER et al., 2019). And looking at the last pre-pandemic statistics, between 28 % (injured), 29 % (fatal accidents) and 49 % (property damage) of accidents in German motorways in 2019 did not happen on dry roads (STATISTISCHES BUNDESAMT, 2020). This makes it clear that there are factors other than traffic participants that need to be considered when analyzing and assessing the performance of ADFs. The focus of this paper is to create a framework which enables assessing data recorded for the usage in scenario-based assessment regarding their representativeness of environmental parameters (cf. Figure 1).

WWW.ITSAMERICAEVENTS.COM/WORLD-CONGRESS

HOSTED BY:

IN PARTNERSHIP WITH:

BUILT BY:

Creating a Framework for the Representativeness Assessment of Automated Driving Safety Assurance

Figure 1: The process for the framework presented in this paper

The limitations of functions by environmental parameters and thereby their reduced operational design domain (ODD) is addressed within the research project Hi-Drive¹ (cf. Figure 2). Here, enabling technologies are to be developed, which address specific limitations such as slippery roads or complex road conditions. But to develop these enablers and to address these ODD shortcomings, knowledge of them and the ability to assess them within recorded data is needed.

The remainder of this paper focusses on describing factors and their potential influence on the performance of ADFs in scenarios. These factors together with recorded data are fed into a framework which allows the assessment of the representativeness of the recorded data regarding these potentially influencing factors. *Related Work* goes into details on the background of scenario-based assessment, scenario parameters and related work. The concept of the framework is described in *A Framework for the Representativeness Assessment of Automated Driving* followed by the description of data sources used as reference for scenario factors in *Data Sources*. A detailed description of the inner workings of the framework as well as some exemplary assessments are presented in *Assessing the Representativeness*. The paper is concluded with an outlook on future work in *Conclusion*.

¹ <https://www.hi-drive.eu/>

WWW.ITSAMERICAEVENTS.COM/WORLD-CONGRESS

HOSTED BY:

IN PARTNERSHIP WITH:

BUILT BY:

Creating a Framework for the Representativeness Assessment of Automated Driving Safety Assurance

Figure 2: The research project Hi-Drive and the gaps within the ODD that are addressed within the project.

Related Work

As stated above, scenario-based assessment has established itself over the past couple of years. A commonly used definition for scenario was established by (ULBRICH et al., 2015) who state that a scenario "describes the temporal development between several scenes in a sequence of scenes". A scene is further defined as a description of the environment at one point in time. This leaves open the gap of how the environment should be described. One take at finding a comprehensive way of describing the environment was done in the German research project PEGASUS, which defined a scenario as a set of five (BAGSCHIK et al., 2018) respective six layers (BOCK et al., 2018), each describing one part of the environment.

However, this description left many things rather vague, and the layer model was strongly focused upon the use-case important within PEGASUS, motorways.

The 6-Layer-Model was further sustained and extended to urban environments by (SCHOLTES et al, 2021) in the research project VVMethoden (cf. Figure 3). Details about the layout of the road are grouped on Layer 1 (Road Network and Traffic Guidance). Any roadside elements are then located on Layer 2, Roadside Structures. Temporal modifications of Layers 1 and 2 can occur, e.g. in construction sites and are grouped on Layer 3, Temporal Modifications of L1 and L2. Traffic participants, their interactions and parameters are grouped on Layer 4, Dynamic objects. Parameters describing for example the weather are grouped on Layer 5, Environmental Conditions and any digital information is grouped on Layer 6, Digital Information.

WWW.ITSAMERICAEVENTS.COM/WORLD-CONGRESS

HOSTED BY:

IN PARTNERSHIP WITH:

BUILT BY:

Creating a Framework for the Representativeness Assessment of Automated Driving Safety Assurance

Figure 3: The 6-Layer-Modell according to (Scholtes et al. 2021)

For the definition of scenarios on Layer 4, there exist approaches to the systematic definition. (WEBER et al, 2019) approach the topic from the aspect of safety and categorize possible scenarios within the scope of possible collisions leading to scenarios defined as relative paths from surrounding positions towards the object. Within the L3Pilot project, scenarios are defined as mutually exclusive instances which together cover the complete duration of a trip within the function's domain (METZ et al., 2019). They are closely related to the scenarios used by (RÖSENER et al, 2019) which are based upon accident types. On the aspect of the other layers, lesser research has been done so far. (HILLER et al, 2021) pick up the topic and conduct an analysis of OpenStreetMap data with the aim of using it for scenario-based testing. An overview of possible parameters and their usage in the testing of a function in an urban environment is done in the VVMethoden project with the OMEGA format² (Scholtes et al, 2022). Even though the focus is on the urban environment, this offers a reasonable categorization and quantification of parameters on the different layers of the 6-Layer-Model.

(PAVELKA et al, 2021) take up the topic of planning the recording of data according to a statistical model. They describe in detail the technology used, the exchange between vehicle and server as well as the analysis but leave the topic of generating a reliable underlying statistical model as an open topic. (DE GELDER et al, 2019) quantifies the degree of completeness of a dataset using the estimated PDFs. However, their focus is on scenarios on Layer 4. Since they don't have any reference, they fall back to estimating it based on kernel density estimation of an unknown distribution.

² https://github.com/ika-rwth-aachen/omega_format

Creating a Framework for the Representativeness Assessment of Automated Driving Safety Assurance
A Framework for the Representativeness Assessment of Automated Driving

As described before, scenario-based testing is the currently used and applicable approach to validation and verification of ADFs. An important part is assuring that the ADF performs well and safe on roads and in interactions with other traffic participants. In terms of the 6-Layer-Model cf. Figure 3) this is Layer 4. Within this paper, the focus is on including parameters from Layers 1 and 5 into the assessment. To this end, a framework is developed which allows a comprehensive analysis of these parameters. In an application of the methodology and the framework, this is shown for Germany. However, the methodology and the framework in general is not limited to Germany. A detailed overview of the framework is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: The framework and its building blocks in detail.

In a first step, the representation of these parameters in recorded data is assessed. Data to be assessed in the framework is available in the L3Pilot Common Data Format (CDF) (HILLER et al., 2019). This format developed in the predecessor of Hi-Drive, L3Pilot, allows storing data recorded about the recording in test drives on public roads as well as information regarding the surrounding traffic. In the currently published version, this format also supports the storage of parameters regarding maps, i.e. Layer 1 parameters. It is therefore extended to include parameters from Layer 5 as well. These additional parameters are added to the recorded statement in an enrichment step. This is done by accessing publicly available data from map and weather providers.

For the interpretation of these parameters, a reference is needed. This can either be manually set or the reference is calculated from statistics. These statistics stem from publicly available statistics or are aggregated over the data sources (map and weather available). As map source, OpenStreetMap³ is used.

³ <https://www.openstreetmap.org>

Creating a Framework for the Representativeness Assessment of Automated Driving Safety Assurance Weather data is collected from the Deutscher Wetterdienst⁴ (German weather service, DWD) and traffic volumes are taken from the counting points (Zählstellen⁵) operated by the Bundesanstalt für Straßenwesen (Federal Highway Research Institute, BASt). Additionally, anonymized statistics on accidents (Unfallatlas⁶) are used. In order to make the framework modular and extendible, the statistics are converted to internal representations of the data for storage. Details on the data sources are presented in Data Sources.

For comparison, these sources are analyzed in detail and aggregated to statistics about German traffic. This is done once when adding a data source and can then be accessed by the framework for comparison with regarded data. For the representativeness, it is possible to switch between weighting factors. On the side of the recorded data, an assessment based on time and on distance is possible. For the aggregated statistics, a weighting based on total length, traffic volume and accidents is possible. Additionally, the proportions and weightings can be set manually for complete layers and single parameters. This can also be done in conjunction with the aggregated statistics, i.e. single aspects of the statistics can be weighted higher or lower.

Using the recorded data and applying the different statistics and aggregation steps is made available using a framework run as a web server. This allows running the framework centrally in an institution and accessing it from various endpoints. Upon loading of the recorded driving data into the framework, it will perform checks on the data in the background and enrich the data with the Layer 1 and 5 parameters if needed.

With the recorded driving data available in the framework, the data can be visualized, and the different representativeness analyses can be triggered. This gives an overview of the data and allows a first assessment of the representativeness regarding single parameters. For more details and documentation purposes, a report on the data can be generated. This report includes in detail all the parameters available from the data as well as potentially their representativeness with the custom weighting, if applicable. Additionally, suggestions can be requested regarding the necessary recording needs in order to achieve full representation of the parameters in the data, as well as the representative proportion regarding one or more parameters.

Data Sources

Within this paper, we use weather, traffic volume and German accidents data recorded in 2019. This year is chosen due to the availability of data from all data sources. Data from 2020 has recently become available, however 2020 was a year with many unforeseen and rare events regarding traffic due to the pandemic so that 2019 was chosen to better demonstrate the framework. Additionally, large parts of the analyzed driving data sets were recorded in 2019 and in the beginning of 2020. The OpenStreetMap data represents the state of the motorways for beginning of 2019.

As stated above, within this paper we focus on Germany and there on motorways. Therefore, some of the data sources named in the previous section presented in detail in this section are limited to Germany. In the following, the data sources are described, and an overview of the included data is given.

For map data, we rely on OpenStreetMap (OSM) within this paper. Whilst there are many different sources for map data available, access to OSM is the most convenient, as it is freely available. This is made possible by an active community which contributes to the further development of the maps and updating existing map parts. However, this also leads to a strong dependency of map quality on the

⁴ <https://opendata.dwd.de/>

⁵ <https://www.bast.de/DE/Verkehrstechnik/Fachthemen/v2-verkehrszaehlung/Verkehrszaehlung.html>

⁶ <https://unfallatlas.statistikportal.de/>

WWW.ITSAMERICAEVENTS.COM/WORLD-CONGRESS

HOSTED BY:

IN PARTNERSHIP WITH:

BUILT BY:

Creating a Framework for the Representativeness Assessment of Automated Driving Safety Assurance engagement of the community. For Germany, previous research (HILLER et al., 2021) showed that the data provided for Germany is accurate for most parameters. Within this paper, the parameters *speed limit* and *number of lanes* are most relevant which both showed to be accurate. Describing the process for the framework in short, the complete extract of Germany is downloaded, data sanitized and the statistics over the various parameters such as speed limit and number of lanes is aggregated.

Figure 5: Locations of counting points and weather stations in Germany used in the framework. Contour Germany: (c) GeoBasis-DE / BKG 2022

Weather data from the German weather service (DWD) is used for the assessment of weather parameters. Across Germany, the data encompasses 1948 weather stations (cf. Figure 5, blue dots) that are regularly updated, and their data uploaded to the DWD servers. The relevant weather data is provided as open data and includes temperature, precipitation, precipitation type, wind speed, sunshine durations and more in varying resolutions (1 minute to annual). The relevant weather parameters currently used within the framework are shown in Table 1 together with the resolutions that are provided.

Table 1: Parameters extracted from DWD data, their description and possible resolution

Parameter	Description	Resolutions
Temperature	Air temperature	10 min, 1 hour
Precipitation	Amount of precipitation	1 min., 10 min.
Precipitation type	Type of precipitation	1 hour
Sunshine duration	Number of sunshine minutes	10 min, 1 hour
Wind speed	Speed of the wind on average and in gusts	10 min, 1 hour
Cloudiness	Total cloud cover in 1/8 steps	1 hour
Visibility	Visibility in meters	1 hour

WWW.ITSAMERICAEVENTS.COM/WORLD-CONGRESS

HOSTED BY:

IN PARTNERSHIP WITH:

BUILT BY:

Creating a Framework for the Representativeness Assessment of Automated Driving Safety Assurance

Another source for judging the significance of scenario parameters for the assessment is the traffic volume per parameter. A data source for quantifying this importance are the counting points (Zählstellen). Across Germany, 2039 of these counting points provide 24/7 coverage of traffic volumes with 880 of those located on federal motorways and therefore relevant in this research. For the framework presented within this paper, we consider the traffic volume based on the hourly data and the average traffic volume based on the annual data. As the locations of the counting points are known (cf. Figure 5, red dots), they can again be matched to other parameters such as weather and map data. The position is matched to the closest weather station thereby mapping the traffic volume to weather parameters. Similar to the procedure for the weather data, the position of a counting point is mapped to the OSM way and enriched with, among others, the number of lanes and speed limit at that part of the motorway. As a result of matching the map data, it can be seen, that the importance of certain map parameters is reduced when taking the relative traffic volume into account (cf. Figure 6). In order to reduce the influence of multiple lanes on the traffic volume, the traffic volume is broken down to single lanes for the comparison. This gives further boost to the claim that other parameters need be considered when assessing the safety of scenarios and their importance for an approval process.

Figure 6: Comparison of road lengths and traffic volume on those roads with lengths provided by OSM and volumes provided by the federal counting points.

In order to better judge the importance of the parameters, accident data is considered as a further data source. Here, the data source is the *Accident Atlas*. This site gives an overview over all accidents with personal injury in Germany for the years 2016-2020. Unfortunately, only starting 2020 all federal states are represented in the data. The data can also be downloaded and analyzed locally which gives us the opportunity to further enrich the provided data and filter it by road types. To achieve this, for each accident location the closest OSM way is determined. Next, we remove the accidents which happened on other types of the road and enrich the kept ones with the Layer 1 parameters, number of lanes and speed limit respectively. Furthermore, provided data contains general information on the road surface and light conditions at the time of the accident. Since the *Accident Atlas* does not provide the exact date and time of the accident, it is not possible to derive accurate weather information for each record in the dataset. To tackle this issue, averaged values of the parameters from Table 1 with resolution 1 hour are used.

WWW.ITSAMERICAEVENTS.COM/WORLD-CONGRESS

HOSTED BY:

IN PARTNERSHIP WITH:

BUILT BY:

Creating a Framework for the Representativeness Assessment of Automated Driving Safety Assurance
Assessing the Representativeness

For demonstration of the framework, we use two driving data sources available to use to demonstrate the utility. They are two datasets available to us internally that were recorded in Germany which we call datasets X and Y here. Combined they cover a total mileage of around 37000 km. The recorded driving data used within this paper is available in the L3Pilot CDF. Among the signals available within the CDF, the location in latitude and longitude as well as the time in a global frame (posix time) are of importance for the enrichment step. Using these signals, the recorded data can be mapped to the parameters on Layer 1 & 5 relevant for this paper. For the map data, this is done using reverse geocoding with the OSM service Nominatim⁷ or using map-matching algorithms on local extracts of map data. For weather data, the enrichment is done by matching the location and timestamp of the vehicle to the closest matching weather station and there to the closest matching recording of weather parameters.

This enrichment step is possible within the framework. However, some of the data recorded in the L3Pilot CDF already contains this data and can therefore be simply extracted from the file and used within the framework. As described above, the framework offers multiple options to assess the representativeness of the parameters and allows an assessment based on different aggregated data. Within this paper, we show the result of the evaluation of the parameters regarding map and weather data for both datasets X & Y. For this purpose, we select a weighting of the parameters based upon distance, traffic volume and accident occurrence.

An exemplary application of this weighting can be seen in Figure 7 for the Layer 1 parameter “Number of Lanes. In the figure, the representativeness of a parameter value (e.g. 3 lanes) regarding a reference is shown. This means, that for the different weighting factors (in blue) this is equal to 1 for all possible values. For the datasets, this differs for each value and is an assessment if that value is under- or overrepresented in the recorded driving dataset. Looking at Figure 7 and the dataset Y (in green) across the different weightings, differences can be seen. Whereas the ratio of representation of roads with more than four lanes weighted by distance is more than 25, for accidents the ratio is never above 3. Interestingly, when looking at the traffic volume, the one lane road sections are the ones overrepresented within dataset Y. Similar conclusions can be drawn for dataset X, although the imbalances are not quite as great. Two lane roads are slightly overrepresented for accidents, but four or more lanes are more clearly overrepresented for distance-based weighting and three lane roads for weighting by traffic volume.

Figure 7: Results of the representativeness of the parameter "Number of lanes" for datasets X & Y with weighting by distance (a), traffic volume (b) and accident occurrence (c)

⁷ <https://nominatim.org/release-docs/develop/>

Creating a Framework for the Representativeness Assessment of Automated Driving Safety Assurance
With these ratios and the travelled kilometers per dataset available, it is possible to assess, if the representativeness of a certain parameter is given. This also allows the derivation of recommendations, assuming, that all already recorded data should be used. This means, that the ratios for all parameter values have to levelled out by recording data on the parameter value itself (if underrepresented) or in all other parameter values (if overrepresented). The result ranges of these calculations can be seen in Table 2. Unsurprisingly, for dataset Y, many additional kilometers would have to be recorded for the representation of the number of lanes to fit the ratios in the different weighting options. Especially for the weighting by distance and traffic volume, not using all data should be taken into consideration as this would lead to necessary recordings of many thousand kilometers, as can be easily deduced from Figure 7. For dataset X, the tendency towards single parameter values is not as distinct as for Y but are still there across all three weightings. This means, that the needed additional kilometers are lower, but still quickly sum up to five digits of additionally necessary kilometers. This further highlights the fact, that careful planning of recordings is important, when using the data while assuming a representativeness of scenario parameters.

Table 2: Ranges of necessary recordings to fit ratio of scenario parameter "Number of lanes" to that of the weighting parameters

Dataset	Weighting	1 Lane	2 Lanes	3 Lanes	4+ Lanes
X	Distance	< 500 km	10k – 50k km	10k – 50k km	0 km
	Traffic volume	0 km	1k – 10k km	1k – 10k km	1k – 10k km
	Accidents	< 500 km	0 km	1k – 10k km	500 – 1k km
Y	Distance	1k – 10k km	> 50k km	> 50k km	0 km
	Traffic volume	0 km	> 50k km	> 50k km	10k – 50k km
	Accidents	< 500 km	10k – 50k km	10k – 50k km	0 km

Similar calculations are possible using the combination of multiple parameters, as long as the joint representation of these parameters and their proportion to the overall mileage is known.

Conclusion

Within this paper we presented a framework for the representativeness analysis of scenario parameters. With this framework, it is possible to analyze existing recorded datasets and assess the representativeness of included scenario parameters. To this end, it allows selecting one or multiple parameters and comparing those parameters using different weightings as reference. This allows to get an overview of under- or overrepresented parameters in a dataset. It also enables the calculation of still needed data with parameter combinations.

For each dataset, the framework can generate a report with suggestions under which environmental conditions, additional data should be recorded. We showed this for one parameter on Layer 1, but the calculation for other scenario parameters is easily possible if the parameter and its distribution are known. Moving forward, we will more closely assess the representativeness of scenario parameters, especially investigating the combination of parameters on different scenario layers. Since the data is already there, this is a task of finding the right combination and weighting of parameters. As before, we will try to base this on as much publicly available data as possible.

Further, we will further extend the framework to cover more parameters and take the evaluation of scenario parameters on Layer 4 into account. This will allow the assessment of driving scenarios regarding their representativeness in all aspects of the ODD, as well as support the research on yet to be covered gaps or shortcomings within the ODD of automated vehicles.

WWW.ITSAMERICAEVENTS.COM/WORLD-CONGRESS

HOSTED BY:

IN PARTNERSHIP WITH:

BUILT BY:

Creating a Framework for the Representativeness Assessment of Automated Driving Safety Assurance

Acknowledgement

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101006664. The sole responsibility of this publication lies with the author(s). The author(s) would like to thank all partners within Hi-Drive for their cooperation and valuable contribution.

References

1. Wachenfeld, W., Winner, H. (2016), "The release of autonomous vehicles", in *Autonomous driving*, pp. 425–449, Springer,
2. Pütz, A., Zlocki, A., Küfen, J., Bock, J., and Eckstein, L. (2017), "Database Approach for the Sign-Off Process of Highly Automated Vehicles," in *25th International Technical Conference on the Enhanced Safety of Vehicles (ESV)*,
3. Zlocki, A.; Eckstein, L. & Fahrenkrog, F. (2015). Evaluation and sign-off methodology for automated vehicle systems based on relevant driving situations, *Transportation Research Record: Journal of the Transportation Research Board, Transportation Research Board of the National Academies*, 123-129
4. Rösener C., Sauerbier, J., Zlocki A., Eckstein, L., Hennecke, F., Kemper, D., Oeser, M. (2019), "Potenzieller gesellschaftlicher Nutzen durch zunehmende Fahrzeugautomatisierung," Sonstige, Tech. Rep. 128,
5. Statistisches Bundesamt, "Verkehrsunfälle Zeitreihen 2019," 2020,
6. Ulbrich, S., Menzel, T., Reschka, A., Schuldt, F., Maurer, M. (2015), Defining and substantiating the terms scene, situation, and scenario for automated driving, in *Proceedings 2015 IEEE 18th International Conference on Intelligent Transportation Systems*. IEEE
7. Bagschik, G., Menzel, T., Maurer, M. (2018), Ontology based scene creation for the development of automated vehicles, in *Proceedings 2018 IEEE Intelligent Vehicles Symposium (IV)*. IEEE, pp. 1813–1820.
8. Bock, J., Krajewski, R., Eckstein, L., Klimke, J., Sauerbier, J., Zlocki, A. (2018), Data basis for scenario-based validation of had on highways, in *Proceedings 27th Aachen Colloquium Automobile and Engine Technology,d*
9. Scholtes, M., Westhofen, L., Turner, L. R., Lotto, K., Schuldes, M., Weber, H., Wagener, N., Neurohr, C., Bollmann, M., Körte, F., Hiller, J., Hoss, M., Bock, J., Eckstein, L. (2021). 6-layer model for a structured description and categorization of urban traffic and environment. *IEEE Access*, 9, 59131-59147.
10. Weber, H., Bock, J., Klimke, J., Roesener, C., Hiller, J., Krajewski, R., Zlocki, A., Eckstein, L. (2019), A framework for definition of logical scenarios for safety assurance of automated driving, *Traffic Injury Prevention*, vol. 20, pp. S65–S70,
11. Metz, B., Rösener, C., Luow, T., Aittoniemi, E., Bjorvatn, A., Wörle, J., Weber, H., Torrao, G. A., Silla, A., Innamaa, S., Fahrenkrog, F., Heum, P., Pedersen, K., Merat, N., Nordhoff, S., Beuster, A., Dotzauer, M., Streubel, T. (2019), Deliverable D3.3 – Evaluation Methods, L3Pilot – Driving Automation,
12. Hiller, J., Müller, F. Eckstein, L. (2021), *Aggregation of Road Characteristics from Online Maps and Evaluation of Datasets*, 2021 IEEE Intelligent Vehicles Symposium (IV), pp. 208-214, doi: 10.1109/IV48863.2021.9575339.
13. Scholtes, M., Schuldes, M., Weber, H., Wagener, N., Hoss, M., Eckstein, L. (2022), *OMEGAFormat: A Comprehensive Format of Traffic Recordings for Scenario Extraction*, 14. Uni-DAS e.V. Workshop Fahrerassistenz und automatisiertes Fahren: 09. – 11.05.2022

WWW.ITSAMERICAEVENTS.COM/WORLD-CONGRESS

HOSTED BY:

IN PARTNERSHIP WITH:

BUILT BY:

SEPTEMBER 18-22, 2022 | LOS ANGELES CONVENTION CENTER
TRANSFORMATION BY TRANSPORTATION

- Creating a Framework for the Representativeness Assessment of Automated Driving Safety Assurance
14. Pavelka, M.; Kletečka, T.; Krejčí, P.; Olšina, J.; Zima, M., Jonis, M. (2021), Automated Statistical Validation Using Big Data, in Proceedings *30th Aachen Colloquium Sustainable Mobility 2021*
 15. de Gelder, E., Paardekooper, J. P., Op den Camp, O., & De Schutter, B. (2019). Safety assessment of automated vehicles: how to determine whether we have collected enough field data?, *Traffic injury prevention*, 20(sup1), S162-S170.
 16. Hiller, J.; Svanberg, E.; Koskinen, S.; Bellotti, F. & Osman, N. (2019) The L3Pilot Common Data Format - Enabling Efficient Automated Driving Data Analysis, in Proceedings *26th International Technical Conference on the Enhanced Safety of Vehicles (ESV)*,

WWW.ITSAMERICAEVENTS.COM/WORLD-CONGRESS

HOSTED BY:

IN PARTNERSHIP WITH:

BUILT BY:

